

1 **A cardiac arrest phenotype in young males with XIAP mutant Crohn's Disease.**

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7 We describe here a molecular signature that accompanies a cardiac arrest phenotype recently reported in
8 young males with inflammatory bowel disease that contain mutations in the XIAP genes that resides
9 immediately downstream of NOD2. We retrieved a gene signature "THUM SYSTOLIC HEART FAILURE
10 DN" when querying the human transcriptome across cellular, tissue and organ setting for XIAP and NOD2
11 or for XIAP only. We also observed enrichment of "THUM SYSTOLIC HEART FAILURE UP" using NOD2
12 and XIAP as bait. Genes of interest that were component gene products of the gene signature included
13 CEP350 and Sbf2.

14 **References**

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